

Becoming Spiritual and Religious In the Later Phase of Human Life - A Study

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ABSTRACT

Spirituality is a significant part of many people's lives, and it can become even more important as we grow older. Spirituality can improve quality of life for seniors. Spirituality is the strong sense of community that is at the heart of most faith groups. People form and strengthen relationships through their faith, whether it's by attending group services or just praying with a friend. Opportunities for social interactions are especially important to seniors, who are at risk of becoming isolated as they age. The religious community is the largest source of social support outside of the family, and involvement in religious organizations is the most common type of voluntary social activity and staying social not only reduces loneliness and depression, but can also potentially reduce the risk of many diseases. The religious social bonds can be particularly comforting during difficult times. Many seniors must cope with the loss of a spouse or loved one. Others might be grappling with their own illness or mortality. Spirituality and Religion can provide a support system for handling these tough issues. Older adults' level of religious participation is greater than that in any other age group. According to United Nations Report 2017 it is estimated that people aged above 60 years will outnumber children under the age 10 by 2030. The Indian elderly population is expected to reach 194 million by 2031 from the existing population of 138 million in 2021. The National Statistical Office report 2021 projects about 41 per cent increase in the elderly population over a decade. This paper is descriptive by nature. The study findings will establish an understanding on role of spiritual and religiousness in later phase of human life.

Key words: Older Adults, Spirituality, Religious, Well-being, Old age, Geriatric

1. INTRODUCTION:

The medical research has discovered the relationship between religion, spirituality and health. Most people do not like to listen about their aging. This is truly due to its associated boost in age, decline in organ function, lack of flexibility, listening, reduced muscular strength, flexibility in pores, skin and blood vessels, wrinkles in the skin etc. But in reality maturation and aging among human beings are inevitable due to life cycle until the demise. Religion is known to be the expression of spirituality. Researchers and clinicians agree that spirituality and fitness have vital connections since persistent sicknesses interrupt one's life causing depression, irritability and lack of hope [1]. Spirituality can be a coping approach against vitality creating resistance to stress associated to diseases [2]. Spirituality helps elderly suffering from illness [3]. Even religious obligation plays vital role in averting physical and mental diseases, recovery, promotion and disease adaptation. Studies have proved impact of spirituality and religious indexes helped in treating cardiac patients, immunity system and self esteem [4][5]. Gallup World Poll surveyed populations in 143 countries (n = 140,000) and found that 92% of people in 32 developing countries indicated religion to be an important part of their life [6][7][8][9]. According to Handbook of Religion and Health, religion includes beliefs, practices, and rituals related to God or ultimate reality. It is a multidimensional construct of belief, behavior, rituals and ceremonies derived from traditions developed over time within a community [10][11]. Spirituality is distinct from humanism, values, morals, and mental health through its connection with god. It is a journey in the path of non consideration and questioning, devotion and surrender. Both religion and spirituality are related to god but spirituality is assessed through well-being, peace, connectedness etc. whereas spirituality is assessed based on the religion [12][13].

1. PROBLEMS OF LATER PHASE OF HUMAN LIFE:

- (a) **Social Problems:** The status of the aged is undermined based on the transformations in the culture, values and living condition. Now technology has gained grounds and elderly are not usually aware on the usage of technology but they just speak over the phone, watch television, listen to music etc. They may encounter problems in communicating with people at distant places through message, picture and videos. Unawareness of technology impedes socialization of the aged [14]
- (b) **Economic Problems:** Aged people from deprived, marginalized and socially and economically backward sections of the society face economic problem due to medical expenses, court cases, education of children, household expenditure etc. Since they engaged in minor jobs with less income not enough to meet their needs. In this regard social security and financial security of the aged is of utmost significance.
- (c) **Psychological Problems:** Societal roles are based on occupation. For instance, a teacher, teach individuals, a doctor provides medical care. With age individuals develop values, norms, principles and impart it to their family and community. The aged people guide others in the right direction and plays a vital role in the progression of the family. Psychological issues such as loneliness, isolation, powerlessness, dementia, depression, social exclusion, anxiety and phobias are haunting elderly.
- (d) **Health Problems:** Aged people experience visual, hearing and speech impairments, decline in word, vocabulary, joint pain, blood pressure etc. Study on the health of Angaminagas found that health is a biological, personal and social concern. With the deterioration of health individuals can lose their independence, social roles, get isolated, experience economic hardship, stigmatized and even get institutionalized.

3. IMPACT OF PRACTICING RELIGION AND SPIRITUALITY:

Religious people believe to have better physical and mental health due to God's intervention. The following are the benefits of practicing religion and spirituality [16]

- (a) **Mental health benefits:** Religion provides positive attitude leading to positive health outcomes, introduces to a meaningful and purposive life imparting healthy behaviour and relationships and the ability to cope with illness and disability. Older adults cope with health problems and life stresses including financial problem, loss of partner etc. hopeful positive attitude about future helps the people with physical problems to recover early. Studies have reported that elderly adopting religious coping mechanism are less prone to depression and anxiety.
- (b) **Health promotion:** Involvement in religious practices maintains better health. For example religious groups such as Mormons and Seventh-Day Adventists advocate the behaviour of avoiding tobacco and alcohol usage hence they live longer than others.
- (c) **Social benefits:** Religious practices foster support networks. Increased social contact with older people detects the disease early due to more community interaction.
- (d) **Caregivers:** Religious faith benefits caregivers. Study on caregivers of Alzheimer disease or terminal cancer found that caregivers with a strong religious faith and many social contacts were better able to cope with the stresses of caregiving.
- (e) **Harmful Effects:** It may promote excessive guilt, narrow-mindedness, inflexibility and anxiety. Religious delusions may develop obsessive-compulsive disorder, bipolar disorder, schizophrenia, or psychoses. Some may experience rejection and existential crisis for example sexual identity. Some religious groups discourage lifesaving therapies such as blood transfusions, treatment of life-threatening infections, and insulin therapy and may substitute it with praying, chanting etc. Rigid religious groups may isolate and alienate older people from family members and the broader social community.

4. LEGAL AND POLICY FRAMEWORK ON ELDERLY WELFARE.

The ageing was first debated at United Nations in 1948 by Argentina and the issue was again raised by Malta in 1969 as a result in 1971, General Assembly asked the Secretary General to prepare a comprehensive report on elderly suggesting guideline to the national and international action. In 1978, Assembly decided to hold a World Conference on the Ageing. Accordingly, the World Assembly on Ageing was held in Vienna from July 26 to August 6, 1982 wherein an International Plan of Action on Ageing was adopted. The overall goal of the Plan was to strengthen the ability of individual countries to deal effectively with ageing in their population considering to the need of the elderly. The Plan attempted to promote social, economic and cultural implications of ageing. The International Plan of Action on Ageing was adopted by the General Assembly in 1982 and called governments to implement its principles and recommendations [17]. In 1992, UN General Assembly adopted the proclamation to observe the year 1999 as the International Year of the Older Persons. It has declared 1st October as International Day of the Older Persons. The General Assembly on December 16, 1991 adopted 18 principles organized into 5 clusters of independence, participation, care, selffulfillment, and dignity of the older persons. India has incorporated following measures.

(a) Constitutional Safeguards: Article 41 states about right to work, education and public assistance against unemployment, old age, sickness and disablement by the state limiting to its economic capacity and development. Article 46 the state shall promote special care in promoting education and economic interest of weaker sections to protect them from social injustice and exploitation [18].

(b) Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007: Central law to by making maintenance and welfare of parents and senior citizens as legal obligation of the children and heirs through monthly allowance. It also provides simple, speedy and inexpensive mechanism for the protection of life and property of the older persons.

(c) Schemes benefitting Elderly: In India, the elderly population is estimated to reach 30 crore by 2050. Government of India has introduced several schemes to the senior citizens [19] in order to improve their quality of life by providing basic amenities including shelter, food, medical care and entertainment. It also aims at capacity building of Government, Non-Governmental Organizations, Panchayati Raj Institutions, local bodies and Community on active aging. The schemes includes Integrated Programme for Older Persons (IPOP), Rashtriya Vayoshri Yojana (RVY), Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme (IGNOAPS), Varishtha Pension Bima Yojana (VPBY), The Pradhan Mantri Vaya Vandana Yojana, Vayoshreshtha Samman, Senior Citizens Saving Scheme (SCSS), National Programme for the Health Care of Elderly (NPHCE), Varishta Mediciclaim Policy. In bus two seats are reserved for Senior Citizens. In Mumbai BEST has provided 5 seats recently. Indian Railways provide 40% fare concession in all Mail/Express including Rajdhani/Shatabadi/Jan Shatabadi trains for Senior Citizens aged 60 years and above for males and 50% to women aged 58 and above. Indian Airlines is providing 50 per cent Discount on Normal Economy Class fare for all domestic flights to Indian senior citizens who have completed the age of 60 years subject to certain conditions.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper stimulates the discussion around the potential for religion, spirituality depicting its role in the later phase of human life. Successful aging refers to dealing successfully with the negative changes in life rather than just facing losses that accompany along the age. Old age is seen as the period of life that is associated with wisdom, philanthropic attitude, and spirituality. Religious practices seem to help individuals to cope with aging-related diseases and help them build up in themselves as a resource. Overall, acknowledging and drawing on the various roles that religion and spirituality play in the lives of older adults can help them in turn to age positively and live their lives in a fulfilling way.

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